

An Analysis of the Legal Framework for the Enforcement of Ethics and Etiquette in Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania

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Abstract:

The enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette is an important aspect in the legal fraternity. The effectiveness of ADR enforcement is also crucial in maintaining consistency within the legal framework, upholding high standards of professionalism, ensuring fairness, and building trust with the public that ADR is the proper mechanism for resolving disputes. In Tanzania, the enforcement of ADR ethics is governed by various laws, such as: - Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (practitioners Accreditors) Regulations, 2021 GN. 147, Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, Regulations, 2021 GN. 148, The Judicator and Application of Laws (Appointment, Remuneration and Disciplinary of Mediators) Rules, 2024 GN. 820, Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118. This article examines the enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania, with particular focus on the challenges arising from the absence of a unified legal framework. Such a gap has led to the fragmentation of ethical and etiquette standards, as well as the disintegration of enforcement powers. In this context, the article also offers recommendations on the way forward.

Keywords: Enforcement, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Etiquette, Ethics, Registrar, Accreditation Panel.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of Alternative Dispute Resolution (hereinafter referred to as “ADR”) has become increasingly common in Tanzania as a mechanism for resolving various disputes. The predominant reasons for its widespread adoption include its ability to save time, its cost-effectiveness, the absence of complex court procedures, and the autonomy it affords to the parties involved. Moreover, ADR often preserves amicable relations between the parties, reducing the likelihood of hostility after the resolution.¹ It is therefore expected that the use of ADR mechanisms will be both effective and enforceable for the parties and practitioners alike. However, despite its many advantages, the ADR process has not been entirely smooth or without difficulties. In practice, ADR continues to face numerous challenges in the resolution of disputes, one of the most significant being the enforcement of its outcomes.² In Tanzania, the enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette faces numerous challenges that hinder the effectiveness and credibility of ADR as a dispute resolution mechanism.³ The existing legal framework has proven inadequate in fully addressing these challenges, thereby limiting the proper enforcement of ethical and professional standards in ADR practice.

This article focuses on the challenge posed by the absence of a unified legal framework in Tanzania. This deficiency has led to inconsistencies among legal practitioners in enforcing ethical and etiquette standards. Consequently, these challenges undermine the primary objective of employing ADR to uphold and enforce such standards. The second section will address the concept of ethics and etiquette, followed by the third section, which will discuss the legal materials and methods related to the enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania. The fourth section will present the results and discussion concerning the enforcement challenges in this context. The fifth and final section will offer recommendations and conclusions.

2. CONCEPT OF ETHICS AND ETIQUETTE

In the context of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), *Ethics* refers to the moral principles and professional standards that guide practitioners in the discharge of their duties with integrity, impartiality, confidentiality, and fairness.⁴ These standards, often codified in legal instruments such as the *Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators* and the *Advocates (Professional Conduct and*

¹ Access to Justice and Legal Aid: Comparative Perspectives on Unmet Legal Need. (2017).

² Mashamba, J. Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tanzania: law and practice. Mkuki na Nyota, Dar es Salaam, 2014

³ Mkundi Legal Aid (2019) Alternative Dispute resolution (ADR) in Tanzania. Available at <https://mkundilegalservice.blogspot.com/2019/02/alternative-dispute-resolution-adr-in.html>. Accessed on July 28 2025.

⁴ Miugua Kariuki (2022) Promoting Professional Conduct, Ethics, Integrity & Etiquette in ADR Available at <https://kmco.co.ke/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Promoting-ProfessionalConduct-Ethics-Integrity-Etiquette-in-ADR.pdf> Accessed on August 2025.

Etiquette) Regulations,⁵ Ensure that ADR processes are conducted in a manner that safeguards the rights of parties and upholds public confidence. *Etiquette*, on the other hand, denotes the accepted norms of professional conduct and decorum observed during ADR proceedings, including respectful communication, appropriate presentation, and adherence to procedural formalities.⁶ While ethics determines what conduct is right or wrong, etiquette regulates how such conduct is expressed. Together, they promote professionalism, enhance the credibility of ADR mechanisms, and contribute to the fair and efficient resolution of disputes.

An effective understanding of ethics and etiquette in ADR must therefore be supported by a strong legal framework that defines, enforces, and harmonises these standards. In Tanzania, the regulation of ADR ethics and etiquette is grounded in various statutes and subsidiary legislation, each setting out obligations, enforcement procedures, and sanctions for misconduct. The following section outlines the principal legal instruments governing this area and the methods by which ethical and etiquette standards are enforced in ADR practice.

3. LEGAL MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 THE RELEVANT LEGAL FRAMEWORK

Due to the persistent violations of ADR ethics and etiquette, it is imperative to establish effective enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance by all stakeholders. The current legal framework governing the enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania is set out in various statutes and regulations, as outlined below.

a) The Civil Procedure Code [Cap. 33, R.E.2023]

This law is fundamental in Tanzania as it provides the legal basis for courts to refer disputes to Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) methods such as arbitration. Specifically, Section 70 of the Code empowers courts to refer disputes to arbitration,⁷ Section 71 further permits the use of conciliation, negotiation, or mediation as alternative methods for resolving disputes outside the courtroom. Moreover, the Code mandates that all civil cases under the Civil Procedure Code (CPC) must first be referred to negotiation, conciliation, mediation, arbitration, or a similar alternative dispute resolution process before proceeding to trial, as stipulated under Order VIII, part C of the CPC.⁸

⁵ GOVERNMENT NOTICE No, 148 Published on 29/1/2021.

⁶ Miugua K. (2022) Op Cit. Pg4.

⁷ The Civil Procedure Code [Cap 33, 2023]

⁸ The Civil Procedure Code [Cap 33, 2023]

b) The Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (practitioners Accreditors) Regulations, 2021 GN. 147

This law provides for the recognition and registration of individuals qualified to perform the functions and duties of reconciliators, negotiators, mediators, or arbitrators in Tanzania. It sets out the qualifications required for registration as a reconciliator, negotiator, or mediator, as well as the accreditation process. Furthermore, the law empowers the Registrar to suspend an accreditation certificate if the holder breaches any terms, conditions, or regulations. Additionally, Regulation 20 grants the Accreditation Panel the authority to deregister any person accredited as a mediator, conciliator, negotiator, or arbitrator in cases of breach of the conditions attached to their accreditation.⁹

c) The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, Regulations, GN. No. 148 of 2021.

This is also a key instrument within the legal framework for enforcing ADR ethics and etiquette standards. Part II of the Regulations provides for the establishment of the Code of Conduct and Practice, setting out the guiding principles for ADR practitioners. Furthermore, this law prescribes the ethical obligations to be observed, thereby ensuring adherence to professional standards in the conduct of reconciliation, negotiation, mediation, and arbitration.

The law imposes sanctions on individuals who commit professional misconduct and sets out the procedures for handling such complaints. It also provides for the right of appeal, allowing an aggrieved party to challenge the decision of the Accreditation Panel where they are dissatisfied with its outcome.¹⁰

d) The Judicator and Application of Laws (Appointment, Remuneration and Disciplinary of Mediators) Rules, GN. No. 820 of 2024

The enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette standards is also provided for under this law. It establishes mechanisms for enforcing the Code of Conduct and prescribes sanctions for breaches amounting to professional misconduct. In addition, the law outlines procedures for lodging complaints, the handling of such complaints, and the scrutiny of relevant documents during the enforcement process.¹¹

⁹ The Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (Practitioner Accreditation) Regulations, 2021

¹⁰ Part III of the Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliator, Negotiators, Mediator and Arbitrators, Regulations, GN No. 148 of 2021

¹¹ The Judicator and Application of Laws (Appointment, Remuneration and Disciplinary of Mediator) Rules, GN No.820 of 2024

e) Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118

This is a legal instrument that prescribes the ethics and etiquette applicable to members of the legal fraternity. Among other provisions, it requires legal practitioners to demonstrate integrity in the performance of their duties, maintain competence and provide quality services, act with honesty, preserve confidentiality, avoid conflicts of interest, and remain impartial. Furthermore, as members of the Bar, practitioners are obliged to uphold professionalism to ensure that ethical and etiquette standards are consistently maintained. This regulation is therefore vital in assessing the conduct of legal practitioners and in evaluating the broader impact of such standards on the community.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 PROCEDURES FOR ENFORCING ETHICS AND ETIQUETTE IN ADR

The enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania is primarily governed by two key legal instruments: GN No. 147¹² And GN No. 148.¹³ The procedures to be followed under these legislations are outlined below.

a. Lodging a Complaint

Rule 14¹⁴ Provides that any person aggrieved by professional misconduct may complain to the Judge in Charge. Furthermore, Rule 8,¹⁵ A complaint of misconduct against a reconciliator, negotiator, mediator, or arbitrator may be submitted in writing to the Registrar. Such a complaint may be made in either Kiswahili or English, using the prescribed Form No. 1 as set out in the Second Schedule to the Regulations.

b. Scrutiny of the Complaint

Upon receipt of a complaint, the next stage is its scrutiny, as provided under Rule 9.¹⁶ At this stage, the Registrar must determine whether the complaint is tenable or frivolous and vexatious, and is required to do so within seven days. Where the complaint is found to be tenable, the Registrar shall notify the complainant of the date and time on which the matter will be presented before the Accreditation Panel. Conversely, if the complaint is deemed malicious or frivolous, the Registrar shall reject it and provide the complainant, in writing, with the reasons for such rejection.

¹² The Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (practitioners Accreditors) Regulations, 2021 GN. 147

¹³ The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, Regulations, GN. No 148 of 2021.

¹⁴ Ibid.

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

Moreover, Rule 15¹⁷ also addresses the scrutiny of complaints, requiring the Judge in Charge to determine whether a complaint is tenable and, if so, to impose sanctions against the mediator as set out under Rule 15(2) (a-d).¹⁸ However, the law is silent on the procedure to be followed where the Judge in Charge finds the complaint to be frivolous or vexatious. It is evident that, at this stage, both the Registrar and the Judge in Charge possess considerable authority, not only to investigate and scrutinize a complaint, but, in the case of the Registrar, also to reject it outright. This concentration of powers and the gaps in the procedural framework will be addressed in the section on challenges encountered in enforcing ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania.

c. Preparation of the Complaint Report and Recommendations

At this stage, the Registrar, having determined that the complaint is tenable, is required under Rule 10¹⁹ to prepare a report accompanied by recommendations and submit the same to the Accreditation Panel. This requirement raises an important question: why should the Registrar provide recommendations on a matter that is to be heard and determined by the Accreditation Panel? What is the intended purpose and potential impact of such recommendations? This concern will be examined further in the section addressing the challenges in enforcing ADR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania.

d. Determination of the Complaint

The law requires the Accreditation Panel to determine a complaint within fourteen (14) days from the date of its receipt.²⁰ The respondent, that is, the person against whom the complaint is made, must be allowed to be heard.²¹ In discharging its functions, the Accreditation Panel may advise the Registrar to investigate the complaint,²² Direct the Registrar to conduct an inquiry, summon the complainant and other witnesses to testify on the matter, and call for any documents relevant to the case.²³

e. Declaration of the Breach of Misconduct

Upon proving the complaint, the Accreditation Panel, through the Registrar, shall issue a declaration that a breach of professional misconduct has occurred. This declaration must be made using the prescribed Form No. 2, as set out in the Second Schedule to the Regulations.²⁴ The consequences of such a declaration against the respondent may

¹⁷ The Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (practitioners Accreditors) Regulations, 2021 GN. 147

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators GN 148 of 2021

²⁰ Ibid, Rule 11(1).

²¹ Regulation 11 (3) of the Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118

²² Regulation 11 (2)(a), of the Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118

²³ Regulation 11 (2)(b), *ibid*.

²⁴ Regulation 12 (1), *Ibid*.

include the issuance of a written warning,²⁵ an order to pay compensation for any loss or cost suffered by the complainant,²⁶ or deregistration from practice.²⁷

4.2 CHALLENGES ARISING FROM THE LACK OF A UNIFIED LEGAL FRAMEWORK

As pointed out earlier, there are several legal challenges facing the enforcement of DR ethics and etiquette in Tanzania. This part will focus on one challenge, which is the lack of a unified legal framework. The same will be in three major categories, which are the fragmentation of the ethical and etiquette standards and the disintegration of powers.

i. Fragmentation of the Ethical and Etiquette Standards

Ethical and etiquette standards are found in various laws, which makes it difficult to point out which one is to be followed and in what situation. More instances are examined below.

ii. Confidentiality

Reconciliators, negotiators, mediators, and arbitrators are required to maintain confidentiality regarding all matters and information disclosed by the complainants, as provided under Paragraph 17 and Paragraph 4 of GN No. 148.²⁸ Additionally, Section 39 of the Arbitration Act²⁹ mandates that arbitrators conduct proceedings in camera to ensure confidentiality. Furthermore, the duty of confidentiality is also addressed under Part V (Sections 29–34) of the Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations, 2018. This illustrates the fragmented nature of confidentiality obligations across multiple legal instruments.

iii. Non-disclosure of clients' information

This is another ethical misconduct that is fragmented under the legal framework in Tanzania. Paragraphs 3 and 13 of GN 148³⁰ require the Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators, and Arbitrators to disclose in writing any circumstances that could potentially give rise to a reasonable apprehension of lack of independence. or impartiality in the resolution of the dispute. In line with that, Rule 109³¹ is also on disclosure of confidential information, which requires an advocate to keep such information confidential and not divulge or use it even after the advocate has ceased to hold such an office.

²⁵ Regulation 12 (a), Ibid.

²⁶ Regulation 12 (b), Ibid

²⁷ Regulation 12 (c), Ibid

²⁸ The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators GN 148 of 2021

²⁹ The Arbitration Act [Cap 15 R.E 2023]

³⁰ Idem, 22

³¹ The Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118.

iv. Duty to Provide Quality Service

This issue clearly shows that the legal framework in Tanzania is not unified. It requires reconciliators, negotiators, and mediators to ensure the parties understand the process, and it is conducted in a manner the parties can participate effectively. This is under Paragraph 5³². Moreover, Rule 12³³ Provides for the same (quality of service), where an advocate is required to deliver quality service to their clients that is expected of a competent Advocate. These are different laws that talk about the duty to provide quality service by the legal practitioners.

v. Impartiality and independence.

On the other hand, Paragraph 14 of GN No. 148 requires arbitrators to conduct proceedings independently and impartially.³⁴ An arbitrator must not represent any party and is obliged to treat both parties equally. Similarly, Rule 46 of GN No. 118 addresses the duty of impartiality for advocates, prohibiting them from representing both sides of a dispute or acting in a matter where they have previously served as mediator or arbitrator.³⁵ These provisions, found in two distinct laws, both emphasize the duties of confidentiality, independence, and impartiality expected of ADR practitioners.

vi. Disintegration of powers.

Although the legal framework in Tanzania confers multiple powers on the Registrar, the Judge in Charge, and the Accreditation Panel, these powers are not consolidated within a single legal instrument. Consequently, they remain fragmented. This is illustrated below:

a. Power to commence disciplinary proceedings *suo moto*

The current legal framework in Tanzania provides for the power to the practitioners to commence ethical disciplinary proceedings on their motion (*suo motu*) in two distinct legislations. First, the Registrar and the accreditation panel have the power to commence disciplinary proceedings on their motion. This power is provided under GN. 148 Rule 8(3).³⁶ Secondly, the same power to commence disciplinary proceedings *suo motu* to the Judge in Charge, this is governed by GN. 820 Rule 14(3).³⁷ This means that the person who is responsible for determining the complaint has the power to complain against you and become the complainant. Here the challenge is that, in such a situation the question is what will be the status of the registrar and the accreditation panel member Judge when he is also a complainant? These are conflicting roles which will impair the process of decision making.

³² The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators GN 148 of 2021.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ The Advocates (Professional Conduct and Etiquette) Regulations 2018 GN. 118.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ The Judicator and Application of Laws (Appointment, Remuneration and Disciplinary of Mediators) Rules, GN. No. 820 of 2024.

b. Power to investigate or scrutinize the complaint

The law, in two distinct legislations, has conferred power to the Registrar and the Judge in Charge to investigate and scrutinize the complaint. The law provides that the Registrar, after receiving the complaint, shall, within seven days, determine whether the same is tenable or frivolous and vexatious. This is provided for under Rule 9(1).³⁸ In line with that, the Accreditation Panel may advise the registrar to investigate the complaint.³⁹ and also advise the registrar to conduct inquiry⁴⁰. This means that the Accreditation Panel has the power to impose power to the Registrar to investigate and carry out an inquiry on the complaint. The main question at this juncture is whether the Registrar has the required expertise to conduct the investigation and come out with credible information or answers that the whole panel can absolutely rely upon and decide? Moreover, under GN No. 820 Rule 15, it also provides that the Judge in Charge shall, within seven days, determine whether the complaint is tenable or frivolous and vexatious.⁴¹

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The enforcement of ethics and etiquette in Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is essential for maintaining public trust, ensuring fairness, and promoting professionalism among practitioners in Tanzania. However, the current regulatory framework is fragmented, with ethical and etiquette standards scattered across multiple laws and regulations. This dispersion creates inconsistencies in interpretation and application, while the overlapping powers of the Registrar, the Accreditation Panel, the Minister, and the Judge in Charge raise legitimate concerns about impartiality in handling complaints. Such structural weaknesses undermine the credibility and effectiveness of ADR as a dispute resolution mechanism.

To address these challenges, it is recommended that the Government of Tanzania enact comprehensive legislation that consolidates the enforcement of ADR ethics and etiquette into a single, coherent legal framework. This unified law should provide clear guidelines on professional obligations, enforcement procedures, and sanctions, while also ensuring a distinct separation of administrative, judicial, and investigative powers. Clarifying these roles would strengthen the principle of impartiality, enhance procedural fairness, and improve consistency in the handling of misconduct cases.

³⁸ The Code of Conduct and Practice for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators GN 148 of 2021

³⁹ Ibid, Rule 11 (2) (a).

⁴⁰ Ibid, Rule 11 (2)(b).

⁴¹ The Judicator and Application of Laws (Appointment, Remuneration and Disciplinary of Mediator) Rules, GN No.820 of 2024

Moreover, the sustainability of ethical ADR practice depends on the competence and integrity of practitioners. Therefore, all ADR professionals should undergo proper and continuous training to fully understand their roles, obligations, and prohibitions under the ethical framework. Such training should incorporate evolving global norms and best practices to keep practitioners up to date. As Mashamba J. notes in *ADR in Tanzania: Law and Practice*, a long-term, sustainable training strategy is key to building a larger pool of skilled and ethical ADR professionals. Finally, the establishment of an independent body specifically mandated to monitor compliance with ethical standards and adjudicate professional misconduct would provide an additional safeguard, further enhancing the integrity and credibility of the ADR process in Tanzania.

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